

**MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS AND CONDITION FACTOR OF *Tilapia zilli*
(PERCIFORMES: CICHLIDAE) OF THE MID CROSS RIVER FLOOD SYSTEM, SOUTH EASTERN
NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The length-weight relationship (LWR) is an important factor in the biological study of fishes and their stock assessments while condition factor is an important component of performance, survivorship and reproductive success in fish, thus the morphometric parameters and condition factor of *Tilapia zilli* was studied between January 2010 and June 2011. The total length-standard length relationship (TL-SL) of *T. zilli* was expressed as $\log(Y) = -0.860 + 1.047 \log(X)$. The length-weight relationship for the individuals ranging in size from 6.5 to 26.3cm TL was estimated. The overall logarithm form of equation obtained was $\log(Y) = -0.783 + 2.438 \log(X)$. The value of co-efficient of correlation ($r = 0.971$) estimated was high. The exponent (b) value indicated negative allometric growth. Condition factor values for the eighteen months of *T. zilli* samples ranged from 1.2 to 4.9 (mean 2.49 ± 0.66). Males had K values between 1.5 and 4.2 (mean 2.47 ± 0.77), while females had values between 1.2 and 4.9 (mean 2.46 ± 0.78). *T. zilli* was in good condition as K values were above 1.0.

KEYWORDS; length-weight relationship, TL-SL relationship, Condition factor, *Tilapia zilli*

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INTRODUCTION

Length and weight data are useful standard outputs of fish sampling programs (Morato *et al.*, 2001). In fish, size is generally more biologically relevant than age, mainly because several ecological and physiological factors are more size-dependent than age-dependent. Consequently, variability in size has important implications for diverse aspects of fisheries science and population dynamics (Erzini, 1994). Length-weight regressions have been used frequently to estimate weight from length because direct weight measurements can be time-consuming in the field (Sinovic *et al.*, 2004). The estimation of population size of a fish stock for the purpose of its rational exploitation often requires knowledge of individual body WLRs in the population (Dulčić and Kraljević, 1996). WLRs have several applications, namely on fish biology, physiology, ecology and fisheries assessment. In biological studies, WLR enables seasonal variation in fish growth to be followed and the calculation of condition indexes. WLR gives us life history and morphological comparisons between different fish species or between different fish populations from different habitats (Petrakis and Stergiou, 1995; Gonçalves *et al.*, 1997; Santos *et al.*, 2002). According to Abdurahiman *et al.* (2004), the LWR is particularly important in parameterizing yield equations and in estimations of stock size. The parameter b of the LWR equation ($W = aL^b$), also known as the allometry coefficient, has an important biological meaning, indicating the rate of weight gain relative to growth in length. Marked variability in estimates of b is usually observed among different populations of the same species, or within the same population at different times. On the one hand, this may reflect changes in the condition of individuals related to feeding, reproductive or migratory activities (King 1995). On the other hand, sampling related factors or calculation methods may often account for the significant difference in estimates (King 1995). Length-weight relationships give

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information on the condition and growth patterns of fish (Mendes *et al.*, 2004). The regression co-efficient (b) for isometric growth is '3' and values greater or lesser than '3' indicate positive and negative allometric growth respectively. Therefore, obtaining accurate LWR parameter estimates is an important factor in the assessment of fish stocks. Length-weight relationships are useful in fishery management for both applied and basic use to (i) estimate weight from length observations; (ii) calculate production and biomass of fish population; and/or (iii) provide information on stock or organism condition at the corporal level. Length-length relationships (LLRs) are also important in fisheries management for comparative growth studies (Moutopoulos and Stergiou, 2002).

In fisheries science, the condition factor is used in order to compare the "condition", "fatness" or wellbeing of fish. Condition factor studies take into consideration the health and general well-being of a fish as related to its environment; hence it represents how fairly deep bodied or robust fishes are. And it is based on the hypothesis that heavier fish of a particular length are in a better physiological condition (Bagenal, 1978). Condition factor is also a useful index for the monitoring of feeding intensity, age and growth rates in fish (Oni *et al.*, 1983). It is strongly influenced by both biotic and abiotic environmental conditions and can be used as an index to assess the status of the aquatic ecosystem in which the fish live. Condition factor is an important component of performance, survivorship and reproductive success in fish. More recently, condition factors have been adopted by ecologists studying fish mating systems under the assumption that they reflect an individual's energetic state and overall quality. Condition factors have been successful at explaining variation in reproductive behaviours and success (Barber, 2002, Kondoh and Okuda, 2002). Fulton's condition factor, K, represents the mass of an individual relative to its body length. K assumes isometric growth in which mass scales to the cube of length (Bryan and Cargnelli, 2004). According to Lizama *et al.* (2002) the study of the condition factor is thus important for understanding the life cycle of fish species and contributes to adequate management of these species and therefore to the maintenance of equilibrium in the ecosystem. Therefore the morphometric parameters and condition factor of *T. zilli* is being studied to provide baseline parameters for management studies, to bridge the information gap lacking about the specie and to study the status of the population of *T. zilli* in the mid Cross river.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Cross River is a major component of the inland waters of South Eastern Nigeria and its role to the fishery of the area is quite significant (Okoh *et al.*, 2007). Cross River originates from Cameroon and flows through Ebonyi State and Cross River State into the Atlantic Ocean. The river (Fig. 1) (Okoh *et al.*, 2007) lies in the area between 5°57" latitude 5°30'20" North and 7°58" longitude 5°30'20" East. The approximate surface area of the Cross River is 3,900,000 ha (Ita *et al.*, 1985). The rainy season and the dry season are the two main seasons of the area.

Sample and Data Collection

The samplings of the *Tilapia zilli* (n = 729) were made by random samples of the catch of the commercial artisanal fishers. The fish samples were collected each month from four sampling locations, Ozizza, Ndibe, Enohia and Uwana in the Cross River basin at Afikpo, Nigeria (Fig. 1). The catches were made using gill nets, cast nets, lift nets, fishing baskets and traps. The samples were sorted and identified to species level using the guides of Olaosebikan and Raji (1998). Fish samples were preserved in 10% formalin as voucher specimens. Total length (TL), Standard length (SL) and Fork length (FL) were measured to the nearest 0.1cm with a meter rule measuring board. Weight measurements were made with a FEJ-1500A electronic compact weighing balance to the nearest 0.1g.

Fig. 1: Map of Afikpo North Local Government Area showing the sampling locations in the Cross River basin (Okoh *et al.*, 2007).

Morphometric parameters

The relationship between length and weight was determined using the power curve:
 $W = aTL^b$ (Sparre and Venema, 1998).

The relationship between the standard length (SL) and the total length (TL) was also determined using the power curve: $TL = aSL^b$ (Sparre and Venema, 1998).

- Where
- W = Body weight in grams
 - TL = Total length (cm)
 - SL = Standard length (cm)
 - b = Slope of the regression line (regression constant).
 - a = Intercept of the regression with the y - axis (regression coefficient).

Regression analysis was used in the estimation of the a and b values and the level of significance of the value of coefficient of correlation(r).

Condition factor (CF)

Fulton’s condition factor was computed according to Ricker (1975) is $K = 100W/ L^3$

RESULTS

Total length-standard length relationship

The total length-standard length relationship (TL-SL) of *T. zilli* with standard length 5.4 - 23.4cm was expressed as $\log(Y) = -0.860 + 1.047 \log(X)$. The value of co-efficient of correlation (r) estimated was 0.985, showing that the TL-SL relationship was highly significant (Fig. 2).

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Fig. 2: Total Length-Standard Length relationship of *T. zilli* in the mid Cross River basin, Nigeria.

Total length-Total weight relationship

The study on length-weight relationships of the *T. zilli* in mid Cross River basin found that the ‘b’ values during January 2010 and June 2011 ranged from 2.467 ± 0.074 and 2.989 ± 0.068 (Table 1).

Table 1 Monthly length-weight relationship parameters of *T. zilli* in mid Cross River basin

Months	N	Parameters		
		a ± s.d.	b ± s.d.	r
Jan 2010	39	-0.180±0.100	2.590±0.095	0.940*
Feb 2010	40	-0.096±0.092	2.511±0.086	0.943*
Mar 2010	35	-0.059±0.081	2.477±0.076	0.959*
Apr 2010	42	-0.015±0.092	2.570±0.086	0.945*
May 2010	41	-0.121±0.096	2.525±0.090	0.939*
Jun 2010	42	-0.044±0.079	2.467±0.074	0.953*
Jul 2010	40	-0.221±0.090	2.672±0.087	0.952*
Aug 2010	40	-0.034±0.063	2.455±0.059	0.971*
Sep 2010	40	-0.390±0.148	2.745±0.141	0.895
Oct 2010	44	-0.147±0.076	2.563±0.073	0.957*
Nov 2010	42	-0.049±0.076	2.483±0.071	0.958*
Dec 2010	41	-0.429±0.159	2.810±0.151	0.886
Jan 2011	40	-0.167±0.097	2.573±0.090	0.950*
Feb 2011	40	-0.105±0.088	2.514±0.078	0.938*
Mar 2011	42	-0.062±0.063	2.855±0.089	0.953*
Apr 2011	40	-0.139±0.095	2.612±0.087	0.948*
May 2011	41	-0.098±0.095	2.543±0.089	0.941*
Jun 2011	40	-0.053±0.083	2.489±0.077	0.960*
Total	729	-0.183±0.093	2.438±0.067	0.971*
Males	309	-0.253±0.091	2.648±0.054	0.879
Females	420	-0.078±0.062	2.547±0.054	0.948*

*P = 0.05 Significant

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The length-weight relationship for the individuals ranging in size from 6.5 to 26.3cm TL was estimated. The overall logarithm form of equation obtained was $\log(Y) = -0.783 + 2.438 \log(X)$ (Fig. 3). The value of co-efficient of correlation ($r = 0.971$) estimated was high.

Fig. 3: Total Length-Total Weight relationship of *T. zilli* in the mid Cross River basin, Nigeria.

Condition factor (CF)

Condition factor values for the eighteen months of *T. zilli* samples ranged from 1.2 to 4.9 (mean 2.49 ± 0.66). Males had K values between 1.5 and 4.2 (mean 2.47 ± 0.77), while females had values between 1.2 and 4.9 (mean 2.46 ± 0.78) (Fig. 4). Condition factor values according to length class

Fig. 4: Monthly condition factor values for *T. zilli* in the mid Cross River basin, Nigeria.

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revealed that the highest values (4.2 and 4.9) were within the length class 9-10 for males and females respectively. Lowest values (1.1 and 1.0) were within the length class 21-22 for males and length class 19-20 for females respectively (Fig. 5). However, all samples of *T. zilli* were in good condition as K values were above 1.0.

Fig. 5: Length-class condition factor values for *T. zilli* in the mid Cross River basin, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION

The parameter *b* of the LWR equation ($W = aL^b$), also known as the allometry coefficient, has an important biological meaning, indicating the rate of weight gain relative to growth in length. According to Hadi (2008), the length-weight relationship of *T. zilli* from Umhfein Lake, Nigeria was computed as $\text{Log } W = -1.9586 + 3.2279 \text{ Log } L$ or $W = 0.011 L^{3.2279}$, ($r = 0.9956$). Basu and Kalu (1999) recorded 2.9696 for the exponent "*b*" in Lake Alau (North Nigeria), while (King, 1996) recorded value of 3.2100 for the same exponent in New Calabar River (Nigeria) for *T. zilli*. The length-weight relationship obtained for *T. zilli* from, Lake Timsh showed the value of "*b*" for male and female and unsexed fish very close to 3, thus reflecting isometry, with highly significant values of the coefficient of determination (r^2) (Mahomoud *et al.*, 2011). Mehanna (2004) recorded exponent (*b*) 3.088 of *T. zilli* in Wadi EL-Raiyan Lakes. The *b* value was 2.9 in Lake Qaurun recorded by Mosaad (1990). Abd-Allah (2000) and Sholloof (2009) recorded the same value of (*b*) = 2.69 in Lake Qaurun and in Edko Lake. In a report on *T. Zilli* at Gbedikere Lake, Kogi State, Nigeria, Adeyemi *et al.*, 2009, obtained the value of the exponent "*b*" to be 3.496, $r = 0.9548$ which were all in contrast to the results of this study in which *b* value was 2.438 indicating a negative allometric growth. In close relation to this study is *T. zilli* in Cross River inland wetlands, Nigeria which had exponent (*b*) of 2.2 (Offem *et al.*, 2009). However, when comparing LWRs, wide variability in parameter estimates for a single species is inevitable. These variables as also seen in other Cichlids (Table 2) may be due to the fact that the LWR is greatly affected by many factors related to population variability and nutritional conditions. The parameters are therefore only useful for the population studies and the awareness of time of sampling is essential. Also it is a well known fact that the functional regression "*b*" value represents the body form, and it is directly related to the weight affected by ecological factors such as temperature, food supply, spawning conditions and other factors such as sex, age, fishing time and area and fishing vessels (Offem *et al.*, 2009).

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Table 2 Comparative results of LWR parameters of other cichlid fishes in different localities.

Species	morphometric parameters	Authors/Localities
<i>Oreochromis aureus</i>	$W = 0.0122 L^{3.109}$	Mehanna (2004) Wadi El-Raiyan Lakes, Egypt.
<i>O. aureus</i>	$W = 0.1625 SL^{2.5104}, r^2 = 0.8349$	Messina <i>et al.</i> (2010) Aguamilpa Reservoir, Mexico.
<i>Tilapia mariae</i>	$W = 0.4500 L^{2.209}, r = 0.7372$ $W = 0.2400 L^{2.757}, r = 0.9502$	Soyinka and Ayo-Olalusi (2009) Badagry Lagoon, Nigeria. Ologe Lagoon, Nigeria.
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	$W = 0.025 L^{2.7}, r = 0.95$	Offem <i>et al.</i> (2009) Cross River inlands wetlands, Nigeria
<i>Tilapia guineensis</i>	$W = 0.01 L^{1.9}, r = 0.92$	
<i>Tilapia mariae</i>	$W = 0.01 L^{3.3}, r = 0.87$	
<i>Sarotherodon galilaeus</i>	$W = 0.006L^{2.2}, r = 0.92$	
<i>Hemichromis fasciatus</i>	$W = 0.0008 L^{2.6}, r = 0.91$	
<i>Hemichromis bimaculatus</i>	$W = 0.08 L^{2.9}, r = 0.88$	
<i>Hemichromis bimaculatus</i>	$W = 0.1 L^{2.14}, r = 0.6201$	Ayoade and Ikulala (2007) Eleiyele Lake, Southwestern Nigeria
<i>Chromidotilapia guentheri</i>	$W = 0.01 L^{3.34}, r = 0.8304$	
<i>Sarotherodon melanotheron</i>	$W = 0.04 L^{2.80}, r = 0.9193$	

The value of the condition factor have been used to measure various ecological and biological factor such as degree of fatness, gonad development and the suitability of the environment with regard to the feeding condition. As stated by Akel and Moharram (2007), monthly variations in condition factor for males and females of *T. zilli* from Abu qir Bay, Egypt were as follows, it is obvious that for males higher values were detected in August (2.11) and November (1.99), meanwhile lower ones were found in September (1.61) and January (1.37). On the other hand, for females, higher values were found in August (2.01); and from October (1.81) to December (1.87) while the lowest value was noticed in September (1.48). It was evident the conformity and nearly similarity between condition factor of both sexes i.e. they had more or less similar trend of increase and decrease. This is closely related to this present study, as the males and females followed nearly the same pattern. Higher K values occurred between March (4.1) for male and June (4.5) for female. This period concised with the onset of the breeding season of *T. zilli* in this study, this indicates the prepareness of the fish towards the spawning season by getting more robust. K values of this present study began to reduce from August towards January. This may not be unconnected to *T. zilli* response to the period of breeding, wherein the specie being a substrate spawner, its feeding activity is reduced. According to Mahomoud *et al.* (2011), the mean values of condition factor for the total length between 8 and 21 for male and 7 to 16 for female of *T. zilli* from Lake Timsah, Egypt ranged between 1.6603 to 2.0190 and 1.6354 to 2.1340 for males and females, respectively. It can be seen that the K values for males data increased at 16cm (2.2019) then decreased gradually,

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followed by an increase up to 19cm (2.0930). The values again declined at 21cm, (1.894) while females recorded a higher value of (K) at 10cm (2.134) followed by decreased then increased at 16cm (2.005). The mean values of the condition factor for *T. zilli* in Umhfein Lake with total length between 15 and 27 cm ranged between 1.9336 and 2.3646. The K values for the combined data dropped at 17 cm, followed by an increase up to 21.5 cm. The values again declined at 23.5 cm, then increased from 26cm onwards the K values gradually increased. The K value (condition factor) for the different size ranged between 1.9336 and 2.3646 with a mean value of about 2.1953 (Hadi (2008). Shallof (2009) stated that the larger the ratio of K, the better is the condition of the fish. From the above the values of K are relatively higher for large fishes than for small ones. This may attributed to sexual maturation and active spawning of the larger fish (Mahomoud *et al.*, 2011). The above K results of other authors based on the size (length-class condition factor values) of *T. zilli* does not agree with the present study as higher K values were found in younger fishes with total length 6 to 18cm while older fishes (18-27cm TL) had lower K values. Mean K value for the combined data of this present study was 2.49 ± 0.66 . Anene (2005) found that K value of *T. zilli* was 4.3 in Umuoseriche lake located in Oguta, Imo State, while Shallof (2009) recorded K value of *T. zilli* as 2.01 in Lake Qarun, Egypt. These differences were due to the different ecological conditions (Mahomoud *et al.*, 2011).

CONCLUSION

The stock of *T. zilli* in the mid Cross river basin is in good condition and show dimensional equality in their growth pattern. The Morphometric parameters as seen in this study can be used in studying growth and population dynamics for this species exploited from this river system.

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